

Workshop

FAIR Metrics in Engineering Sciences

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Track B1 „How to be FAIR: FAIR play integrated right from the start“

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Contributors of today's workshop, that would like to be named (name + affiliation) in a publication about this workshop

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What is 'engineering' for you - which digital objects do you work with?

"F": Findable for Engineering Sciences

F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R.1 below)

F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes

F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

Anything else about Findable?

"A": Accessible for Engineering Sciences

A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a **standardized communication protocol**

A1.1. the **protocol** is open, free, and universally implementable

A1.2. the protocol allows for an **authentication and authorization procedure**, where necessary

A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

Anything else about **Accessible**?

Contact person in case of problems accessing data (esp. many years after the data was deposited)

"I": Interoperable for Engineering Sciences

11. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable **language for knowledge representation**

Thesaurus?

•
useful

••
important

•••
essential

12. (meta)data use **vocabularies** that follow FAIR principles

ERA
Vocabulary

<https://www.sciology.ih.edu/sciolog/era2/collections/ERA1/NG&antofake&p.agen=1>

Dublin
Core?

•
useful

••
important

•••
essential

13. (meta)data include **qualified references to other (meta)data**

Links to
parent
datasets

•
useful

••
important

•••
essential

Anything else about **Interoperable**?

File Format?

some data from proprietary software has problems with older versions -> e.g. Inventor, interoperable standards?

data from proprietary software could lead to problems (e.g. CAD-data)

"R": Reusable for Engineering Sciences

R1. (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant **attributes**

dublin core

ISO 19115

•
useful

••
important

•••
essential

R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible **data usage license**

task for legal department of institutes/universities?

Creative Commons

•
useful

••
important

•••
essential

R1.2. (meta)data are associated with **detailed provenance**

•
useful

••
important

•••
essential

R1.3. (meta)data meet **domain-relevant community standards**

DIN/ISO references?

SensorML

•
useful

••
important

•••
essential

*Anything else about **Reusable**?*

code reproducibility, virtual environments to reproduce code later, "preservation" ?

Voting: To which area might such a metric apply?

Any feedback? Feel free to place it here - thank you!

Thank you!
Nicely
prepared,
great input

great idea to
collect input from
the community,
waiting for the
output/excited
about the result :)

Thank you!!
Very good
design of all
slides/
materials!

Thanks for
the great
workshop!